

Deliverable D3.5 Extended toolkit

Project Title (Grant agreement no.):	ELIXIR-CONVERGE: Connect and align ELIXIR Nodes to deliver sustainable FAIR life-science data management services (871075)		
Project Acronym (EC Call):	ELIXIR-CONVERGE (H2020-INFRADEV-2018-2020)		
WP No & Title:	WP3 Common Data Management Toolkit		
WP leader(s):	Frederik Coppens (VIB), Carole Goble (UNIMAN)		
Deliverable Lead Beneficiary:	2 - VIB		
Contractual delivery date:	31/01/2023	Actual delivery date:	19/06/2023
Delayed:	Rescheduled		
Partner(s) contributing to this deliverable:	VIB, UiO, UNIMAN, UU/SU, DTLs, ÚOCHB		
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Reviewers:	ELIXIR-CONVERGE Management Board (MB) members.		

Log of changes

DATE	Mvm	Who	Description
14/06/2023	0v1	Frederik Coppens (VIB), Flora D'Anna (VIB)	Initial version
19/06/2023	0v2	Frederik Coppens (VIB), Flora D'Anna (VIB)	Sent to PMU after incorporating internal WP feedback
05/07/2023	0v3	Nikki Coutts (ELIXIR Hub)	Circulated to the MB for final review before submission
13/05/2023	0v4	Frederik Coppens (VIB), Flora D'Anna (VIB)	MB comments addressed
13/05/2023	1v0	Nikki Coutts (ELIXIR Hub)	Final version to be uploaded into EC Portal

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1. Executive Summary

The scope of Deliverable D3.5 is two-fold: firstly, the extension of the content of the WP3 data management toolkit, known as RDMkit, based on the second wave of demonstrator use cases from WP5; and secondly, the harmonisation of the content achieved through collaboration among Research Data Management (RDM) professionals and experts from different countries and institutions (WP1). This collaboration aims to discuss, establish, and share common best practices, ensuring that RDMkit content remains comprehensive and aligns with international standards.

As already reported in ELIXIR-CONVERGE D3.2 report on “Toolkit extension based on first wave demonstrators”, the second wave of demonstrator use cases from WP5 have previously been added, with the exception of the Toxicology data demonstrator. The extension described in this report adds both general and domain-specific best practices, guidelines and examples since the D3.2. Integrations with other resources and dissemination activities and impact are described in the ELIXIR-CONVERGE D3.3 report on “Single entry-point portal for the toolkit for all stakeholders” and the D3.4 report on “Dissemination of the toolkit across the ERA”.

The work detailed in this deliverable was carried out during four hybrid events organised after July 2021, aimed at extending, harmonising, and enhancing the toolkit. These events provided the platform for collaborative efforts to build upon the achievements of Deliverable D3.2 “Toolkit extension based on first wave demonstrators” completed in July 2021.

Other WPs and external partners have greatly contributed to the extension and harmonisation of RDMkit. Some of the RDM topics listed by WP1 for the final version of best practices and guidelines have already been included in RDMkit, while other topics are currently in preparation for publication. The final WP5 second wave demonstrator use case (Toxicology data) has also been added to the toolkit. The ELIXIR-CONVERGE WP9 and members of the BY-COVID project contributed to the RDMkit by sharing best practices on management of human pathogen genomics data. ELIXIR Nodes and Communities (Intrinsically Disordered Proteins, Microbial biotechnology, Proteomics, Rare diseases, Galaxy), as well as members of the research infrastructures (Instruct-ERIC, EuroBioImaging and BBMRI), have published content to “your domain” and “tool assembly” sections. Overall, since July 2021 the RDMkit has been extended mainly via the addition of 5 domain pages, 5 task pages, 5 tool assemblies, 16 National resources pages and many revisions to existing pages.

For this deliverable, the editorial board improved the way references to tools and resources are managed in RDMkit. With the new system, the links to tools and resources are machine-actionable, therefore managing tools and resources in RDMkit is now a more automated, traceable, robust, less error prone and a sustainable process.

Although the main intended product for this deliverable is RDMkit, the Jekyll theme called ELIXIR Toolkit Theme (ETT) powering RDMkit has had a great impact and has been used and deployed by several infrastructure providers and communities: WorkflowHub project (EOSC-Life), Infectious Diseases Toolkit (BY-COVID), 1+MG Trust Framework, FAIRDOM, ELIXIR Nodes and organisations (Norwegian Life Science RDM LookUp, Australian BioCommons How-to-Guides, ERIM Research Toolbox, ELIXIR-UK Fellowship, Code Reproducibility Training).

In conclusion, the extended and harmonised RDMkit serves as a valuable resource for research data management in the life sciences. It acts as a central hub, integrating various ELIXIR RDM resources and beyond, providing guidance and best practices. The success of RDMkit is evidenced by the strong interest from communities and the increasing contributions received. RDMkit's strength lies in its lightweight and open machinery for supporting processes and linkages, allowing RDM professionals from different countries, organisations, and domains to collaborate and share common best practices. The extension and harmonisation of RDMkit are achieved through the incorporation of diverse RDM best practices and the integration with other RDM resources, enhancing its capabilities and promoting consistent data management practices.

The impact of RDMkit can be evaluated based on the contributions from various communities and organisations, as well as the recommendations from funders. Numerous ELIXIR Nodes, communities, platforms, and EU projects have embraced RDMkit, making it a central resource for the new ELIXIR RDM community.

The next steps for RDMkit include scaling up its content, keeping it up-to-date, and ensuring community engagement. The recently established ELIXIR Research Data Management Community aims to maintain and extend RDMkit's content while facilitating the sharing of common knowledge. Sustainability strategies are being explored, including content coordination with other ELIXIR resources and establishing a governance system for the RDMkit Alliance¹ which was announced at BioITWorld 2023.

Furthermore, a publication about RDMkit and its processes is being prepared.

2. Contribution toward project objectives

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following objectives/key results:

Objective no. / Key Result no. Description	Contributed to:
Objective 1: Develop a sustainable and scalable operating model for transnational life-science data management support by leveraging national capabilities (WP1, WP5)	
Key Result 1.1: Established European expert network of data stewards that connect national data centres and similar infrastructures and drive the development of interoperable solutions following international best practice, including national interpretations of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)	Yes
Key Result 1. 2: Development of joint guidelines and common toolkit that are adopted into funder recommendations, with support available nationally and in local languages	Yes

¹ https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/rdmkit_alliance

Key Result 1.3: The catalogue of successful national business models incorporated into national strategies	No
Key Result 1.4: The developed “sustainable and scalable operating model for transnational life-science data management support” is adopted into national ELIXIR Node	No
Objective 2: Strengthen Europe’s data management capacity through a comprehensive training programme delivered throughout the European Research Area (WP2, WP6)	
Key Result 2.1: A comprehensive ELIXIR Training and Capacity building programme in Data Management, directed at both data managers and ELIXIR users, and connected to the national training programmes in Data Management in the ELIXIR Nodes and prospective ELIXIR Member countries.	No
Key Result 2.2: Development of a collective group of trainers that support scalable deployment of Data Management training across ELIXIR Nodes.	No
Key Result 2.3: A substantial cohort of data managers, Node coordinators and researchers with specific data management skills, business planning and knowledge of transnational operations across the ELIXIR Nodes	No
Objective 3: Align national data management standards and services through a sustainable, scalable and cost-effective data management toolkit (WP2, WP3, WP5)	
Key Result 3.1: Assemble a full-stack harmonised common toolkit comprising all aspects of data management: from data capture, annotation, and sharing; to integration with analysis platforms and making the data publicly available according to international standards.	Yes
Key Result 3.2: Provide exemplar toolkit configurations for prioritised demonstrators to serve as templates for future use.	Yes
Key Result 3.3: Establish national capacity in using as well as updating, extending and sustaining the toolkit across the ERA.	Yes
Key Result 3.4: Enable ‘FAIR at source’ practice for data generation, and analytical process pipeline implementation by flexible deployment of the toolkit in national operations	Yes
Objective 4: Align national investments to drive local impact and global influence of ELIXIR (WP4,WP6)	
Key Result 4.1: Development of a Node Impact Assessment Toolkit based on RI-PATHS methodology.	No
Key Result 4.2: Adoption of Impact assessment in ELIXIR Nodes, supported by Node coordinators network and feedback on applicability from dialogues with national funders.	No

Key Result 4.3: Creation of national public-private partnerships and industry outreach where open life-science data and services stimulate local bioeconomy	No
Key Result 4.4: Growth in reach, impact and engagement of stakeholder communication assessed by established ELIXIR Communications metrics	No
Key Result 4.5: Initiating and advancing discussions on Membership (EU and international) or strategic partnerships (international countries) following ELIXIR-CONVERGE workshops.	Yes

3. Introduction

3.1 Scope of the deliverable

The scope of this deliverable is to describe the approach and results of i) the further extension of the RDMkit, with a focus on content from the 2nd wave demonstrator use cases, and ii) the harmonisation of the content as best practices and guidelines, beyond its first state. Additional content, integrations with other resources and, overall, the final toolkit will also be described.

The knowledge gained from the demonstrator use cases is presented in the RDMkit as pages in 'your domain' and 'tool assembly' sections. The harmonisation of the best practices and the integrations with other resources resulted from the collaboration and the knowledge exchange among professionals in RDM and stewardship in life sciences, across numerous countries and institutes.

3.2 Relationship with other WPs

The RDMkit has been a powerful and unifying information resource for WPs 1-5 and for the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project as a whole. All these WPs have contributed to the design, content, oversight and extension of the RDMkit.

- WP1 Data Management experts contributed to content extension via addition of harmonised best practice and guidelines, mostly in "your tasks" pages.
- WP2 Training experts led work on improving pages about different roles and job profiles in RDM in "your role" section; they also deepened the connection between the RDMkit and TeSS, the ELIXIR Training Portal. WP2 also developed the video "ELIXIR-CONVERGE - The why of research data management" and short videos "RDMbites" disseminating RDMkit.
- WP4 assisted in outreach, the RDMkit communication planning and connections with EC, NIH ODSS (USA) and other national policy makers. RDMkit is recommended by [8 national funders](#)² (see column F of the spreadsheet).
- WP5 contributed to content extension via addition of best practices and guidelines for the management of specific data types in different research domains, such 2nd waves demonstrator use cases and beyond.
- WP8 contributed to the Tool Assembly page on European COVID-19 data portal
- WP9 created a task page on data brokering and a domain page about management of human pathogen genomics data.

²<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1RfgY4yxXlZhiYYVV-IJtp2EQ5bqii9Ss9IHJOqf6OAw/edit#gid=1702293238>

3.3 Methodology applied for extension and harmonisation of the toolkit

For the extension of the RDMkit, the same successful methodology described in ELIXIR-CONVERGE D3.2 report on “Toolkit extension based on first wave demonstrators”, was applied. The additional methodologies applied for the extension and the harmonisation are described below.

3.3.1 National resources

During Biohackathon 2021, the editorial board designed the first template to include information about National RDM resources. A metadata schema to describe tools developed and/or provided at National level was implemented in the markdown page template. A new way of listing pages was developed together with a way to link and visualise national tools with the main toolstable.

3.3.2 Page templates

The RDMkit editorial board generated, re-structured, and standardised templates for each section in RDMkit, namely “Your task template”, “Your domain template”, “Your role template”, “Tools assembly template” and “National resources template”. The templates are available both as markdown pages and Google documents accessible via the “Ways to Contribute” section in RDMkit. The templates have been a key tool to facilitate compliance to content and metadata structure with minimum need for curation by editors. The templates now do not only outline the expected structure for the page, but also contain references to the contribution guide and instructions on how to add metadata and links to other resources.

3.3.3 Contentathon and gap analysis

Both the editorial board and the experts from WP1 data management network performed gap analyses to identify key RDM topics missing in the RDMkit. The identified topics were then used as topics to work on during events, such as “Contentathons”. During contentathons, RDM professionals and researchers from different countries and institutes worked together to discuss, agree and write RDM best practices and guidelines in RDMkit. The editorial board and the WP1 data management network invited experts in the topics identified in the gap analysis, so that relevant content could be added to RDMkit for the benefit of the scientific and RDM community at large. Members of WP5 have joined the contentathons to include the 2nd wave demonstrator use cases to RDMkit. Two hybrid contentathons have taken place in December 2022 (in Luxembourg) and May 2023 (in Ghent), respectively - see ELIXIR-CONVERGE D3.4 report on “Dissemination of the toolkit across the ERA” for a complete list of the RDMkit events.

3.3.4 Integrations with other ELIXIR resources

Extension and harmonisation of RDMkit via integrations with other relevant ELIXIR resources, specifically DSW and FAIR Cookbook, have been done as described in ELIXIR-CONVERGE D3.3 report on “Single entry-point portal for the toolkit for all stakeholders”.

3.3.5 Machine-actionable reference to tools and resources

The RDMkit editorial board designed a new system to manage tools and resources mentioned in RDMkit. This new system makes the tools and resources machine-actionable by organising them in a structured YAML file and by assigning them an internal identifier. Therefore, referencing tools and resources become more standardised. The transition toward this new system is in progress and close to its conclusion. Full implementation and documentation of the new system will be completed by the end of the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project.

3.3.6 More intuitive and user friendly landing page with focus on search

A new landing page was designed to make clear that the toolkit has many, equally important entry points to all the RDM guides. A more prominent distinct search-bar should also attract researchers to easily find specific content on the website.

4. Description of work accomplished

4.1 Working sessions to extend and harmonise the toolkit

Since July 2021 (Deliverable D3.2 Toolkit extension based on first wave demonstrators), 4 events have been organised in order to extend, harmonised and improve the toolkit:

- 2021 November, BioHackathon project for writing RDMkit pages on national resources and exemplar tool assemblies. Moreover, an UX expert's assessment on the RDMkit website was carried out; this led to the design of the new RDMkit landing page.
- 2022 November, BioHackathon project for improving RDMkit and FAIR Cookbook integration: "*The What & How in data management: Improving connectivity between RDMkit and FAIR Cookbook*"; preprint DOI 10.37044/osf.io/emc2f.
- 2022 December, Editors F2F Hackathon and hybrid Contentathon: review of the site structure, management of tools and resources, and functionality improvements. Content review and development in various RDMkit sections has also been performed.
- 2023 May, Editors F2F Hackathon and hybrid Contentathon: implementation of the new system to manage tools and resources. Content review and development in various RDMkit sections has also been performed.

4.2 Interaction with other WPs and external partners

In the ELIXIR-CONVERGE project, members of other WPs contributed to extend and harmonise RDMkit. During the "ELIXIR-CONVERGE WP1 & WP8/9 F2F meeting" on September 21st-23rd 2022 in Padova, WP1 compiled a list of topics (e.g. ethics, file formats, README files, etc) that would be included in the final version of the best practices and guidelines. Those topics have been worked on during the latest Contentathon in May 2023 in Ghent. During the latest Contentathon, WP9 drafted content about best practices to manage human pathogen genomic data, sharing knowledge derived from BY-COVID project; WP2 worked on restructuring and improving the information on the "Your role" section. WP5 included the 2nd wave demonstrator use cases.

Additional Communities contributed with content, as domain page and tool assembly: Intrinsically Disordered Proteins (IDP), Microbial biotechnology, Proteomics, Rare diseases, Galaxy.

Members of the research infrastructures Instruct-ERIC, EuroBioImaging and BBMRI contributed with content in "Your domain" and "Tool assembly" section (Structural bioinformatics domain page, Bioimaging data domain page, MOLGENIS and OMERO tool assembly page, respectively).

The USA NIH ODSS recently funded a project to bootstrap USA contributions and is identifying RDMkit "anchor" leadership in the USA. An NIH ODSS representative serves on the RDMkit Editorial Board at the invitation of the Board .

Projects, communities and institutions reached out to WP3 members in order to reuse the Jekyll theme "ELIXIR Toolkit Theme (ETT)", powering RDMkit, for other knowledge base websites and documentation: WorkflowHub project (EOSC-Life), Infectious Diseases Toolkit (BY-COVID), FAIRDOM; Nodes and institutions (Norwegian Life Science RDM LookUp, Australian BioCommons How-to-Guides, ERIM Research Toolbox, ELIXIR-UK Fellowship).

4.3 Dissemination activities

A complete overview of the RDMkit dissemination activities up until May 2023 can be found on the ELIXIR-CONVERGE D3.4 report on “Dissemination of the toolkit across the ERA”.

A [poster](#)³ about RDMkit was presented at the ELIXIR All Hands Meeting 2023. Moreover, the workshop “[How ELIXIR services help with real world challenges in FAIR data and software management](#)”⁴ helped identify gaps and missing topics in RDMkit. This information will be used by the RDMkit editorial board and the ELIXIR RDM Community to improve RDMkit content.

5. Results

A summary of the latest RDMkit (website) release can be found at [v2.0.0 - New landing page and better navigation](#)⁵.

5.1 RDMkit content extended

5.1.1 Second wave demonstrators: domains and tools assembly

The 2nd wave demonstrators, described in the project proposal, have been added as pages under the section “Your domain”. The domains of the 2nd wave demonstrator use cases are: Marine metagenomics, Human genomics data (Human data), Biomolecular simulation data and Toxicology data. Since the last report (D3.2), the final demonstrator use case about toxicology data has been added to RDMkit as a domain page (Toxicology data).

³<https://f1000research.com/posters/12-682>

⁴<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1bK2PAPbErqH5t3puJwJFVDW2FaklLqwepmdYgxPiOAQ/edit#heading=h.8yacamuak08k>

⁵<https://github.com/elixir-europe/rdmkit/releases/tag/v2.0.0>

The screenshot shows the RDMkit website interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Data management' highlighted, and links for 'About', 'Contribute', and 'GitHub'. A search bar is also present. On the left, a sidebar menu lists various data management categories, with 'Toxicology data' selected and highlighted in pink. The main content area is titled 'Your domain: Toxicology data'. Below the title, there is a list of sub-topics: Introduction, Data from in vitro assays - Data analysis and modelling, Data from animal assays - Existing data and vocabularies, Data from human assays - Existing data and vocabularies, Ecotoxicology data - Existing data, Related pages, More information, and Relevant tools and resources. Below this list, the 'Introduction' section begins, explaining that toxicology focuses on the adverse effects of chemicals on living organisms.

Figure 1: Second wave demonstrator use case (CONVERGE-WP5): Toxicology data. Complete list of the domain-specific pages.

5.1.2 Additional domains and tool assemblies

In addition to the demonstrator use cases, four domain specific-pages have been added by other research communities: namely, Bioimaging data, Proteomics, Rare disease data and Structural bioinformatics (Figure 1).

Four new tool assemblies have been added to RDMkit (Figure 2).

1. **OMERO.** The OMERO tool assembly illustrates an example of institutional repository for scientists, researchers and data stewards to handle their imaging data in a secure central way. This tool assembly has been described by members of the EuroBioImaging (UK) infrastructure.

2. **Galaxy.** The Galaxy tool assembly showcases how the Galaxy platform can support scientists to perform accessible, reproducible, and transparent computational analysis. This tool assembly was provided via the collaboration with the ELIXIR Galaxy Community.

3. **Molgenis.** The Molgenis web application is one of the ELIXIR Recommended Interoperability Resources (2021). The related tool assembly in RDMkit explains how to use Molgenis scalable software infrastructures to capture, exchange, and exploit the large amounts of data that is being produced by scientific organisations.

4. **Plant Phenomics.** The plant phenomics tool assembly covers the whole life cycle of experimental plant phenotyping data and aims to help everyone in charge of plant phenotyping data management to enable the integration of phenotyping data with other omics data, the findability of their data in plant specific (e.g. FAIDARE) or generic search portal (e.g. Google Data Search), and the the long term reusability of their data.

Galaxy	MOLGENIS
Galaxy is an open, web-based platform for accessible, reproducible, and transparent computational research.	Molgenis is a modular web application for scientific data. Flexible data integration platform to find, capture, exchange, manage and analyse scientific data.
Related pages ▾	Related pages ▾
Affiliations:	
OMERO	Plant Phenomics
OMERO is a software platform for managing, sharing and analysing images data.	Tool assembly for managing plant phenomic data.
Related pages ▾	Related pages ▾
Affiliations:	

Figure 2: Four new tool assemblies added to RDMkit.

5.1.3 Additional tasks and national pages

Additional “Your tasks” pages (Figure 3).

- Costs of data management.
- Data provenance.
- Data brokering: contribution from WP9.
- Project data management coordination: result of the RDM Focus group, organised through WP1 (May-June 2022) , with external contributions.
- Machine actionability: result of the RDM Focus group, organised through WP1 on 24th September 2021, with external contributions.

“National resources” pages (Figure 3).

The following 16 Countries/Nodes have added information about County-specific RDM resources in RDMkit: Belgium, Czech Republic, Estonia, Finland, Ireland, Luxembourg, Norway, Sweden, Switzerland, Germany, Spain, France, Italy, Netherlands, Portugal, and United Kingdom.

Figure 3: Overview of National resources and Your tasks pages in RDMkit.

5.1.4 Additional content

Additional RDMkit pages that have been recently written during the “RDMkit Contentathon in May 2023 in Ghent” are still at the draft stage:

- Your tasks: Best practices for Open and FAIR ML/AI
- Your role: IT/research software engineer (RSE), Principal Investigator
- Your domain: Human pathogen genomics

New paragraphs on the following existing pages are also being added: Structural bioinformatics, Human data (ethics, GDPR compliance), your role pages, data organisation (“how to write a README file”, “how to choose appropriate file formats”), Documentation and metadata (“how to apply ontologies in practice”), Data protection (information security).

5.1.5 Integrations

A complete overview of the RDMkit integrations up until April 2023 can be found on the ELIXIR-CONVERGE D3.3 report on “Single entry-point portal for the toolkit for all stakeholders”.

5.2 Harmonised content

The RDMkit content has been collaboratively developed by various communities and organisations that have actively engaged in discussions and reached a consensus on the best practices and guidelines for research data management. Consequently, the content within RDMkit can be regarded as harmonised across different countries, institutions, and communities. Furthermore, RDMkit is seamlessly integrated with and contains links to several ELIXIR resources that are highly valuable for RDM (see ELIXIR-CONVERGE D3.3 report on “Single entry-point portal for the toolkit for all stakeholders” and ELIXIR-CONVERGE D3.4 report on “Dissemination of the toolkit across the ERA”). This integration ensures that RDMkit is aligned and harmonised with the broader RDM ecosystem.

RDMkit is community-driven, with a growing list of 167 contributors who have contributed 109 pages, managed by an Editorial Board of 15 editors, with representatives from ELIXIR and the NIH Office of Data Science Strategy.

Countries/Nodes that have contributed to RDMkit are: ELIXIR-BE, ELIXIR-CH, ELIXIR-CZ, ELIXIR-DE, ELIXIR-EE, ELIXIR-ES, ELIXIR-FI, ELIXIR-FR, ELIXIR-GR, ELIXIR-IE, ELIXIR-IT, ELIXIR-LU, ELIXIR-NL, ELIXIR-NO, ELIXIR-PT, ELIXIR-SE, ELIXIR-SI, ELIXIR-UK, EMBL-EBI.

Other organisations and projects that have contributed to RDMkit are: NIH/OD, INSTRUCT-ERIC, BY-COVID, EuroBioImaging.

5.3 Machine-actionable reference to tools and resources

As a result of the new system to manage tools and resources in RDMkit, the use of a tool or a resource for a specific task in RDM will become more clear for the readers and fully embedded in the RDMkit content (paragraphs). Each tool and resource will be highlighted and accessible from the text directly, in addition to being listed in the “tool and resource” table at the end of each page (Figure 4). This will ensure that all the listed tools maintain their context on the website, thus reducing the lengthy tool lists at the bottom of the page and enhancing their usefulness to the visitor. Moreover, the management of the links to tools and resources in RDMkit will be more machine-actionable, automated and less error prone. Moving from a Google spreadsheet to a GitHub yaml file increases editorial control and decreases the risk of unintentional corruption of information. The information about contributors who add tools and resources will now be recorded as well. This is because adding tools will be incorporated into the same submission process as adding new content, thereby improving traceability and transparency.

Solutions

- Make your code available. If you have to develop a software for your data analysis, it is always a good idea to publish your code. The git versioning system offers both a way to release your code but offers also a versioning system. You can also use Git to interact with your software users. Be sure to specify a license for your code (see the [licensing section](#)).
- Use package and environment management system. By using package and environment management systems like [Conda](#) and its bioinformatics specialized channel [Bioconda](#), researchers that have got access to your code will be able to easily install specific versions of tools, even older ones, in an isolated environment. They will be able to compile/run your code in an equivalent computational environment, including any dependencies such as the correct version of R or particular libraries and command-line tools your code use. You can also share and preserve your setup by specifying in a [environment file](#) which tools you installed.
- Use container environments. As an alternative to package management systems you can consider *container environments* like [Docker](#) or [Singularity](#).
- Use workflow management systems. [Scientific Workflow management systems](#) will help you organize and automate how computational tools are to be executed. Compared to composing tools using a standalone script, workflow systems also help document the different computational analyses applied to your data, and can help with scalability, such as cloud execution. Reproducibility is also enhanced by the use of workflows, as they typically have bindings for specifying software packages or containers for the tools you use from the workflow, allowing others to re-run your workflow without needing to pre-install every piece of software it needs. It is a flourishing field and [many other workflow management systems](#) are available, some of which are general-purpose (e.g. any command line tool), while others are domain-specific and have tighter tool integration. Among the many workflow management systems available, one can mention
 - Workflow platforms that manage your data and provide an interface (web, GUI, APIs) to run complex pipelines and review their results. For instance: [Galaxy](#) and [Arvados](#) ([Common Workflow Language \(CWL\)](#)-based), open source.
 - Workflow runners that take a workflow written in a proprietary or standardized format (such as the [Common Workflow Language \(CWL\)](#)) and execute it locally or on a remote compute infrastructure. For instance, [CWL in Toil](#), the reference CWL runner ([cwltool](#)), [Nextflow](#), [Snakemake](#), [Cromwell](#).
- Use notebooks. Using notebooks, you will be able to create reproducible documents mixing text and code; which can help explain your analysis choices; but also be used as an exploratory method to examine data in detail. Notebooks can be used in conjunction with the other solutions mentioned above, as typically the notebook can be converted to a script. Some of the most well-known notebooks systems are: [Jupyter](#), with built-in support for code in Python, R and Julia, and many other [Jupyter kernels](#); [Rstudio](#) based on R. See the table below for additional tools.

environment file which tools you installed.

- Use container environments. As an alternative to package management systems you can consider *container environments* like [Docker](#) or [Singularity](#).
- Use workflow management systems. [Scientific Workflow management systems](#) will help you organize and automate how computational tools are to be executed. Compared to composing tools using a standalone script, workflow systems also help document the different computational analyses applied to your data, and can help with scalability, such as cloud execution. Reproducibility is also enhanced by the use of workflows, as they typically have bindings for specifying software packages or containers for the tools you use from the workflow, allowing others to re-run your workflow without needing to pre-install every piece of software it needs. It is a flourishing field and [many other workflow management systems](#) are available, some of which are general-purpose (e.g. any command line tool), while others are domain-specific and have tighter tool integration. Among the many workflow management systems available, one can mention
 - Workflow platforms that manage your data and provide an interface (web, GUI, APIs) to run complex pipelines and review their results. For instance: [Galaxy](#) and [Arvados](#) ([Common Workflow Language \(CWL\)](#)-based), open source.
 - Workflow runners that take a workflow written in a proprietary or standardized format (such as the [Common Workflow Language \(CWL\)](#)) and execute it locally or on a remote compute infrastructure. For instance, [CWL in Toil](#), the reference CWL runner ([cwltool](#)), [Nextflow](#), [Snakemake](#), [Cromwell](#).
- Use notebooks. Using notebooks, you will be able to create reproducible documents mixing text and code; which can help explain your analysis choices; but also be used as an exploratory method to examine data in detail. Notebooks can be used in conjunction with the other solutions mentioned above, as typically the notebook can be converted to a script. Some of the most well-known notebooks systems are: [Jupyter](#), with built-in support for code in Python, R and Julia, and many other [Jupyter kernels](#); [Rstudio](#) based on R. See the table below for additional tools.

Galaxy

Open, web-based platform for data intensive biomedical research. Whether on the free public server or your own Instance, you can perform, reproduce, and share complete analyses.

[Website](#) [Tool info](#)

How can you use package and environment management systems?

Figure 4: Preview of a section from the “Data analysis” page in RDMkit deploying the new system to manage reference to tools and resources.

5.4 ETT: a template for many communities

RDMkit’s technological core is based on an open-source, re-usable website template, which is called the ELIXIR Toolkit theme (Figure 5). The theme abstracts the functionality of the RDMkit site and makes it available for others to create a similar site with their own content. The theme is open source and has the permissive MIT use licence. Our theme has already been used by several groups: WorkflowHub project (EOSC-Life), Infectious Diseases Toolkit (BY-COVID), FAIRDOM, ELIXIR Nodes and organisations (Norwegian Life Science RDM LookUp, Australian BioCommons How-to-Guides, ERIM Research Toolbox, ELIXIR-UK Fellowship).

Figure 5: ELIXIR Toolkit Theme (ETT) powering RDMkit.

5.5 Data Stewardship Wizard

During the development of the Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW), significant strides have been made to enhance collaboration among researchers and improve overall efficiency. One notable new feature is the ability to comment on questionnaires, facilitating better collaboration between researchers and data stewards. This feature allows researchers to discuss as well as provide feedback, suggestions, or clarification on specific questions, enabling data stewards to understand the researchers' needs more effectively and tailor their support accordingly. By fostering open communication and collaboration, the DSW creates an environment that promotes efficient data stewardship and maximises the value of research data.

Figure 6: Comments about a question in the DSW questionnaire

Furthermore, the development of the DSW has focused on improving the process of document template creation and related debugging for data stewards. DSW now offers embedded tools for creating templates that adhere to best practices in data stewardship. Additionally, the debugging functionality assists data stewards in identifying and resolving any potential issues or inconsistencies within the templates. These improvements not only save time for data stewards but also ensure that the data management process is carried out in a structured and reliable manner, maintaining the integrity and quality of research data.

Figure 7: Document Template Editor in DSW

The development of the DSW has also prioritised enhancing the flexibility of knowledge models, allowing for customizable phases and metrics. This new level of flexibility enables data stewards to adapt the knowledge models to the specific needs of different research projects, institutions, or domains. By providing configurable phases and metrics, the DSW ensures that the data stewardship process remains relevant and effective in diverse research contexts. Researchers and data stewards can now tailor the project workflow and assessment criteria to align with their unique requirements, ultimately leading to more accurate and meaningful results.

Figure 8: Summary report showing metric values

Figure 9: Phase selection based on how they were defined in the knowledge model

Moreover, the integration with RDMkit has been done in a flexible way, allowing for easy configuration of DSW instance linked with RDMkit or its forks. This integration facilitates seamless data flow and interoperability between the DSW and other research data management tools, providing researchers and data stewards with a unified and efficient ecosystem.

6. Conclusions

RDMkit acts as a central signpost, allowing users to navigate the landscape of ELIXIR RDM resources (and beyond), which includes the DSW, FAIR Cookbook, TeSS, bio.tools and FAIRsharing. The strong interest shown by communities and the ever-growing list of RDMkit Domain, Tasks, Tool Assembly and National Resource pages is clear evidence that such guidance was needed.

The strength of RDMkit lies in the lightweight and open process machinery that are suitable to host knowledge and best practices. RDMkit’s participatory processes lower the barriers for contribution so that RDM professionals across Countries, organisations and domains can formalise and share common best practices.

The extension and harmonisation of RDMkit is accomplished through two key elements:

1. The incorporation of common and domain-specific RDM best practices from diverse scientific communities across different countries. This collaborative effort brings together valuable insights and expertise, resulting in an enriched and comprehensive toolkit.

2. The integration of RDMkit with other existing RDM knowledge resources further enhances its capabilities. This integration facilitates seamless data management practices by providing researchers with access to a broader range of tools and methodologies.

By combining these elements, RDMkit promotes consistent and efficient data management practices, fosters collaboration, and facilitates the widespread adoption of standardised approaches within the research community.

RDMkit is designed and developed with sustainability in mind. The site technology is intentionally kept simple and the site infrastructure is kept separate from content as a modular and reusable site theme. ELIXIR nodes have included both the RDMkit content and infrastructure in their service delivery plans, which provides a roadmap and resources for sustainability.

7. Impact

The impact of the extended and harmonised RDMkit can be evaluated based on: i) the content contributions received by several communities and organisations, ii) by the funders and national organisations that recommend RDMkit as a valuable resource for RDM and iii) by the number of users.

Contributing communities and organisations include:

- 19 ELIXIR Nodes. Moreover, the RDMkit has become a “Node service” for the following ELIXIR nodes: Belgium, Norway, Sweden, and UK.
- ELIXIR communities and focus groups including: 3D-BioInfo, Marine Metagenomics, Microbial biotechnology, Plant Sciences, IDP, Proteomics, Human Data and Toxicology. Health Data, Machine Learning and Biodiversity pages are in the pipeline. RDMkit is the rallying point for the emerging RDM Community.
- ELIXIR platforms: RDMkit is a flagship for Data, Interoperability and Training Platforms, and signposts the Tools Platform resources.
- ELIXIR EU projects: EOSC4Cancer, EJP-RD, AgroServ and BY-COVID are committed to use RDMkit. BY-COVID and 1+MG framework are already using the ETT theme.
- Other EU Research Infrastructures: EuroBioImaging and the BioExcel centre of excellence manage pages on imaging and biomolecular simulation. Members of INSTRUCT-ERIC contributed to the Structural bioinformatic page (currently, a draft page). EU-IBISBA plan pages on Industrial Biotechnology.
- The USA NIH ODSS recently funded a project to bootstrap USA contributions.

Recommendations by funders include: Horizon Europe programme guide (26/06/211) and the ERC guidelines for Open Research Data and Data Management Plans. Nationally, RDMkit is recommended by [8 national funders](#)⁶ (column F).

Detailed and complete statistics on RDMkit usage can be found in the ELIXIR-CONVERGE D3.4 report on “Dissemination of the toolkit across the ERA”, under the “Results” and “Impact” section.

⁶<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/1RfgY4yxXlZhiYYVV-IJtp2EQ5bqii9Ss9IHJOqf6OAw/edit#gid=1702293238>

8. Next Steps

The challenge that the RDMkit success brings is to scale up this content, keep it up to date and keep the contributing communities engaged. To address these challenges we will explore different models for content and community governance.

8.1 ELIXIR Research Data Management (RDM) Community

In May 2023, the ELIXIR Research Data Management (RDM) Community was established. The members of the RDM Community are RDM professionals, in ELIXIR and beyond, that aim to discuss and agree on common best practices and guidelines for RDM in Life Sciences. The Community is committed to maintain and extend RDMkit content and to use this resource as a means to share common knowledge. Further details on the RDM Community activities can be found in the [Community White Paper draft](#)⁷.

8.2 Possible sustainability strategies

A way forward for content coordination and the maintenance of the links with other ELIXIR resources, such as FAIR Cookbook, TeSS and DSW, will be established together with ELIXIR Platforms, taking into account their 2024-2028 strategy programmes.

Given that RDMkit currently operates as a Node Service across multiple ELIXIR Nodes, it is essential that the respective Nodes demonstrate commitment towards sustaining the resource's deployment (GitHub repository) and/or maintaining the editorial board's activities. This possibility has been discussed among the Nodes.

The ELIXIR Toolkit Theme (ETT) is currently a Node Service only for ELIXIR Belgium. However, the broad adoption of ETT in several Nodes and European projects will require a governance system to sustain the resource.

Since not only the theme, but also the content is of interest for many communities, and the spawning of further RDMkits is becoming a possibility, together with the NIH ODSS a RDMkit Alliance was announced at BioITWorld, and aims to be functional in 2024⁸.

8.3 RDMkit paper

A publication about RDMkit and its processes is currently in preparation (RDMkit: The Research Data Management Toolkit for Life Sciences).

9. Deviation from Description of Action

Not applicable.

⁷<https://drive.google.com/file/d/1ZXVZhF-KgZvsrHQ-oPlitvC8R0ZCe-L/view?usp=sharing>

⁸https://rdmkit.elixir-europe.org/rdmkit_alliance

